

**METHODS OR DEVELOPING SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION
SKILLS AMONG PUPILS IN SECONDARY EDUCATION.
SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION TYPES**

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Annotation: This article provides information Methods or developing simultaneous translation skills among pupils in secondary education and simultaneous translation types.

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Along with developed countries, our native language is one of the international languages with high hopes of adding to our native Uzbek language from other foreign languages and on the contrary, directly from Uzbek to a foreign language, that is, without the use of any other language translation activities are developing rapidly with images. Especially long Since ancient times, the field of written translation has been widely practiced in our country was. But in recent years, with the demand of the times, including translation the weight of simultaneous translation is growing. "Simultaneous translation issues" The purpose of the subject is to teach the student from Uzbek to a foreign language, from a foreign language to Uzbek the ability to translate quickly, accurately, adequately, logically into the language formation. The task of science in this direction is, first of all, interpretation simultaneous translation activities for gifted students, its principles, strategies, introduction to theoretical concepts, practical instructions consists of giving. The subject of science is simultaneous translation and related theoretical, is reflected in practical issues. First of all, the concept of "simultaneous translation", which is the subject of science. Simultaneous interpretation is one of the most complex types of

interpreting in this type of translation, the translation is performed using special equipment. This is a continuous speech without an interpreter when the speaker is speaking is a method of interpreting the content to the audience. Simultaneous translation system. Special equipment is a system of simultaneous translation, which is usually stationary or in the form of a folding booth, where there are two pairs of headphones and an interpreter for the microphone, again as well as the number of participants in need of translation depending on the set of headphones or portable receivers. Interpreters are especially small during the conference sounds in the room to suppress the speaker's own voice wear insulating headphones. Sound amplifier The translation is delivered to the listeners' ears by. From technology with the participation of adults, according to the translation that has been launched and the production of products in a large conference hall or auditorium, viz conferences, seminars, presentations, etc. There are six official languages of the United Nations: Arabic, Chinese, English, French, Russian and Spanish. UN Congress Hall and everyone change the translation system in conference halls. One for each language. There is a work booth. There are a total of six booths for each of the six languages. There are three interpreters in the booth. Simultaneous translation. Translation advantages that differ from the way the simultaneous translation works there is: Implement the speaker's speech without interruptions. That's the speaker to keep the audience's attention, the reaction of the audience and allows you to feel the mood. By rescheduling the event reduced by a factor of two. Convenience for participants, currently learning a foreign language not infrequently, many participants present their reports in a foreign language prefer to listen. In a coherent translation, the speaker pauses and translates continues to irritate such participants. The disadvantage of simultaneous translation In turn, the translation has some disadvantages, too consists of:

The cost of simultaneous translation is much higher than that of serial translation. This includes the cost of translation services and special equipment

as part of the rent. A minimum of 2-3 people who are familiar with the theme of the event translators will need to be involved. High data loss and low level in simultaneous translation the information does not reach the listener.

Topic questions:

1. What is simultaneous translation?
2. What is the subject of "Problems of simultaneous translation"?
3. What is the purpose of the subject "Problems of simultaneous translation"?
4. What are the tasks of the subject "Problems of simultaneous translation"?
5. What are the components of a simultaneous translation system?
6. What are the advantages and disadvantages of simultaneous translation?

Simultaneous translation research is different from other studies in applied linguistics carried out without. This is because of the many languages and situations methodological problems arising from its existence. From this in addition to teaching these languages and acquiring oral communication skills compared to the large market of applied linguistics in need of new methods practical application of research results required for a small number of users provided. Preliminary details of the translation activity. The work studied is theoretical for the training of specialists in this field created under the pen of professional translators who tried to lay the foundation. But fifty after the first attempts at simultaneous translation analysis. Although more than a century has passed, the scientific community has not studied any of this process far from the consensus on the suitability of the paradigm. Synchronous with the complex task of studying it because of the unique qualities of translation colliding practitioners are forced to come up with many different theoretical ideas were First, simultaneous translation of existing models into existing models emphasis is placed on the relative application. Especially with translation successful in complicating the process of listening and speaking synchronization Second, the semantic and in an environment of linguists and translators who are very well versed in structural differences the possibility of an instantaneous, accurate translation of the discourse is emphasized. Of a time Simultaneous translation is

characteristic of oral speech, which distinguishes it from written speech and revealed differences in need of linguistic research. Simultaneous translation research has traditionally gone in two directions. Translation practitioners and teachers based the Paris school on the interpretive theory of translation has taken a normative socio-pragmatic approach. It was held in Germany in 1946 after the end of World War II The Nuremberg International Military Court was the first in the trial of the Nazis simultaneous translation was used. This is the first time in the whole world the use of simultaneous translation in a large-scale international event. Many international organizations emerged after World War II the emergence of an unexpected demand for effective language mediation brought. According to some authors, the use of simultaneous translation when the idea was first expressed, critics were skeptical of its acceptability looked at. But after the demonstration of simultaneous translation capabilities programs for the immediate training of simultaneous interpreters were developed. First and practitioners should set professional and academic standards came Individual manuals published in the first stage are still classics remains an example (Rosan 1956, Herbert 1965). Types of simultaneous translation.

In practice, there are three types (variants) of simultaneous translation: 1. Simultaneous translation of Yoda (hearing). In this case, the interpreter through headphones accepting the speaker's continuous speech and depending on how the information falls performs blocking translation. This is the most common and most complex condition.

2. Synchronize according to the text with or without prior preparation translation. The simultaneous interpreter receives the text of the speaker's written speech in advance and translates according to the given materials.

3. Simultaneous reading of pre-translated text. Simultaneous interpreter speaker reads a pre-prepared text after the speech. In places where the speaker deviates from the original text during the speech makes corrections. Features of simultaneous translation. Simultaneous translation is one of the most important types of translation feature high efficiency, original text speech and translated speech the interval

between is on average 3-4 seconds. At most 10 seconds. Therefore, the speaker is guaranteed to speak without interruption. There is no outside influence on the speaker's opinion and from the speech will not stop. This is so that the listeners fully understand the speech allows. This is why simultaneous translation is now a common practice in the world has become a method of translation. Today, 95% of the world's international meetings, simultaneous translation is used in conferences. However synchronous translation has a great deal of scientific and expertise, and it is usually formal synchronous translation is extremely important because it is used in international conferences high demands are placed. Simultaneous translation requirements. Simultaneous translation from the interpreter while he is speaking in the original language a short period of time based on thematic knowledge along with listening comprehension quickly predict, comprehend information in the original language, it needs to be stored in memory and redirected. However different international conference, meetings, simultaneous interpreter "lightning thinking" will be able to do and have high speaking skills. IAIC (International Simultaneous Interpreters Association) decision, simultaneous interpreter can only translate 80% of the content of the participant-speaker is considered successful.

The strategy of probabilistic forecasting in case of simultaneous translation is the attempt of the translator to foresee and work out lexical, grammatical, phonetic components of the speech of the speaker before they are pronounced, basing on already received and processed (i.e. translated) information. One of the methods of probabilistic forecasting is determination of any parts of speech in the text of the speaker. This method is especially productive when the main and semantic information of the statement is focused at the end of the sentence. For the first time the term "probabilistic forecasting" has been used by Russian scientist, the famous physiologist. According to Chernov's definition "probabilistic forecasting" is "A situation is a signal for preparation of body to react adequately to B situation. The wider range of the events which were equally often following A in the past (i.e. more uncertain is the forecast), the broader range of physiological systems will be

mobilized in response to A signal. This prospective adaptation to actions in the forthcoming situation 198 relying on probabilistic structure of last experience can be called "probabilistic forecasting". In Chernov's opinion mechanism of probabilistic forecasting is psycholinguistic mechanism providing simultaneous translation. This phenomenon is also widely investigated in the works of the academician Anokhin who claims that adaptive qualities which differ in the sequence and repeatability of events are inherent in all live organisms in the course of evolutionary development. We are convinced that process of implementation of probabilistic forecasting needs to be considered in the context of a real communicative situation as it differs in a combination of extra linguistic factors in the communication process. According to Chernov, it is possible to select set of elements or factors in a communicative situation of simultaneous translation which are identified in case of the response to the following questions: 1) who? 2) what ... with? 3) what subject? 4) before whom? 5) whom? 6) where? 7) when? 8) what purpose? 9) why? The translator needs to know the responses to these questions for successful implementation of the simultaneous translation. Probabilistic forecasting is multi-level, hierarchically connected mechanism each particle of which is in close connection with another. The probability of the correct forecasting increases in case of redundancy of the message and on the contrary, goes down in case of its insufficiency. It should be noted that, probabilistic forecasting is possible only if the text of the speaker consists of closely interconnected units. Sdobnikov and Petrova write that redundancy of language is shown at different levels. For example, at phonemic level: after one or two consonants there should be a vowel in Russian. At grammatical level: in the phrase "As the interconnected methods of any interconnected methodology..." the phenomenon of numerous sequences of words in gender, number and case, i.e. repetition of gender indication, number and case in a few words is observed. The conjunction "as" assumes appearance of the sentence, which will contain the consequence. The translator perceives the speech thanks to the necessary level of redundancy, providing thereby a possibility of probabilistic

forecasting. It should be noted that availability of context increases redundancy that gives opportunity to the translator to perform probabilistic forecasting with accuracy that is more precise. "Being included to context, the Russian word form loses on average 1,6 units of the grammatical information containing in forms of the extra text word". Piotrovsky and other researchers established the redundancy reasons: 1) repeatability in speech flow of certain elements; 2) interdependence of linguistic components of the message. The fact that the sequence of components of the message (sounds, words, phrases, sentences and meanings) is formed on the basis of certain rules that make them interdependent, and leads to the fact that the source of the message is repeated.

Conclusions:

These conclusions are also basic provisions of theory of communication. Speaking about sub classification of probabilistic forecasting, it is worth mentioning that scholars differentiate two of them: a) "linguistic", or "syntactic" forecasting based on forecasting of a source of continuation of a discourse from knowledge of standard set of phrases and set expressions, such as undertake an obligation to... leave without a leg to stand on..., to functional words and unions which help to realize the meaning of statement; b) "extra-linguistic" forecasting based on external knowledge, extra-linguistic data which are possessed by the translator.

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